

THE IMPORTANCE OF GAMES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. *In this article, it is considered that the use of games is the key to success in teaching foreign languages to students.*

Key words: *linguistic games, small groups, sunflower game, blackboard, let's play together, idea.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ИГР НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается, что использование игр является залогом успеха в обучении студентов иностранным языкам.*

Ключевые слова: *языковые игры, малые группы, игра в подсолнухи, доска, поиграем вместе, идея.*

Nowadays, in our country, which is rapidly developing day by day, there is an increasing demand for specialists who perfectly master foreign languages. Therefore, much attention is paid to teaching the younger generation of foreign languages even in the period from preschool to higher education.

Looking back at our past years and intoxicating it, we notice that in education we are going through a period of total renewal and adaptation to it.

In today's dynamically developing education, we need advanced pedagogical technologies, as well as advanced teachers, so that we can kill the fire and bring it to high heights in every possible way. Learning and teaching foreign languages is a long and perfect process. It requires regular work from a person and work on oneself. It is clear that the use of various interactive techniques in the process of teaching foreign languages to cultivate oral skills makes language learning a girlish and hobby.

To increase the wealth of students' speech in a foreign language and its effectiveness, it is advisable to use educational games in the lesson. From experiments it is known that the game expands the imagination when learning a new language, makes it possible to think and speak the same language. With the help of the game, it is possible to restore words forgotten in memory. Games that are played in small-to-small groups or in general can be used in the lesson or in circle training during the lesson process. This in turn will not fail to pay off of course. When playing alone and finding a solution to a problem, the reader feels a real feeling of joy. And team games teach to achieve success and liberalize speech.

In linguistic games, it is possible to grow an oral and written defect in students, generating situations of communication.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Games or game-style exercises conducted in a foreign language all open the way to the magical world of words. Therefore, I think that everyone who says that I will be a real foreign language teacher should be creative, that is, it is always possible to adapt to the knowledge of students without using the same games, changing their words every time, choosing the optimal one, creating new ones and generally using these games to make the lesson more interesting and interesting.

In such lessons and circle classes, students will never get bored and fully attend the lesson, while looking forward to the next lesson. Below I want to illustrate some of the games I use for my students who are learning English in their free time from class and also recommend them to my peers who want to become teachers in the future:

1. Game "sunflower". In this game, students are divided into groups of 4-5 people. The teacher, based on the subject of the subject, throws one problem in the middle. Each group

makes a sunflower and sticks leaves, placing a circle in its center. Depending on the topic, each group on the circle is written one common problem and glued to the board. In the allotted time, the groups together write their thoughts on a leaf and place it in a flower where that group problem is written. This technique can be used to explain the topic covered, reinforce and repeat it, and to identify the knowledge acquired by readers.

In our next game, the task is performed in pairs. In this, the first participant gives his name in a foreign language, and the second participant adds his own name to him, saying the name of his comrade.

For example:

First reader: My name is Jeremie

Second Reader: His name is Jeremie and my name is Nicole, and others. The game will continue on this throne. From such games can be spent at the beginning of the school year with students who are just getting acquainted. Through this, they learn in English the names of their fellow citizens as well.

What is your name ? What is your hobby? and in the game, the participants sit in a circle. This will require a soft small ball. In this, the presenter races the ball to one of the participants. The reader who received the ball should say his name and talk about himself. Then he shoots the ball to another participant. And the reader who fails to fulfill the condition comes out of the game

For example:

1. My the name is Ruslan. I like drawing.
2. My name is Anne .I like reading books
3. Meningism im..... I like it.....

It is possible to apply such as (dancing, playing football, a list of music, going to the movies, going to the theater, playing chess).

Team games.

The purpose of this game, which is played without using the word “Yes” or “No”, is to expand the imagination of students, increase their creativity, teach them to ask questions. 2 or more teams participate in the game with their 5 or 6 players. The first participant of one of the teams gets to the middle and introduces himself, and the members of the opposing teams ask him questions that will be answered with a short “yes” or “no”. The player, on the other hand, must apply other answer options to these questions instead of using the word “yes” or “no”. 1 question and answer lasts about 30 seconds and is done very quickly. The player should not be given a chance to think. The person who is running the game must check whether the player who is answering, depending on the hour, is responding to his questions in 30 seconds or a minute. If a player answers questions quickly without using the word “yes” or “no” for a minute, he is considered the first to score, otherwise he is considered a loser. And a score is added to the reader who asked the question. The points scored are calculated by each reader or team.

The questions to ask can be as follows:

Opponent: do you have a cat?

Player: Of Course!

Opponent: do you love him?

Player: Although Not!

Opponent: is his color black?

Player: Completely

Second game:

Group adventure: Have you ever gone to Tashkent?

Joueur 2: Of Course!

Group adverse: do you like that place?

Joueur 2: I haven't seen a place yet!

Groupe adverse: have you watched The Fountains?

Joueur 2: I didn't have time!

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Team games are much more complex and readers can use dictionaries. But no special manuals are required to run these games. And the participants in the game will need paper and a pen.

Technique “LET’S STUDY TOGETHER”. In this case, the training group is divided into small groups. In each small group there will be an expert and will teach others. The goal of each group is to fully assimilate the knowledge of the participants of all other groups on the topic.

The structure of the process of organizing work in groups using the “LeT's study together” technique:

1. Depending on the level of knowledge, groups of different types are formed, consisting of 3-5 people.

2. Each group is assigned one task.

3. Within each group, a common assignment is distributed.

4. Everyone performs an Individual Assignment.

5. Mini-lectures of all group members are listened to.

The overall result is formed and prepared for its presentation.

In addition to these games, it is possible to achieve the expected results if the following types of exercises are also used:

1. Place the pictures on the basis of the given words - instead.

2. Work in pairs, apply vocabulary in dialogues.

3. Exercises that teach independent thinking (describe, draw or write down the house or apartment of my dream).

3. Listen and stage the dialogue.

4. Find the flaw in the image. Write a letter to the artist, finding how he made a mistake.

5. Hear opinions and express your attitude towards him. And hakozo is such a type of exercise, which can be continued again with a creative approach.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that in order to create the spirit, mood of the competition in the classroom, it is advisable for the teacher to announce the result of the games once a month and hold the final competition. But it should be remembered-the most important thing in all games is not victory, but participation.

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